

Title: Blockchain & Bitcoin.

Name: Jason Butcher

Affiliation: Experienced payments and blockchain entrepreneur, driven to make the world a better place.

BIOGRAPHY:

Jason Butcher A seasoned professional with over two decades of hands on experience starting business with the last 15 years in the electronic payments, fintech, and financial markets. Specializing in entrepreneurship, business development and creating connections Jason strives to bring individuals, markets and opportunities together on a global level. Priding himself on his keen abilities as a solution and problem solver, Jason enjoys mentoring fellow entrepreneurs and advises local and international startups. Jason is the COO of CoinPayments and is the founder of Parallel Payments. He is an active member of the Blockchain association of Canada and the fintech advisor for the National Crowdfunding association of Canada. He contributes to many entrepreneurs as a mentor and is an advisor to several organizations raising capital through ICO's and traditional financing.